

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

D6.2 Report on the Results of the DSS for the Case Study Sites

VERSION 2

Acknowledgment: This project is part of the PRIMA Programme supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 1923.

Disclaimer: The content of this publication is solely responsibility of the authors and it does not represent the view of the PRIMA Foundation.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8207725](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8207725)

Project Information

Project Title	Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean		
Project Acronym	InTheMED	Grant Agreement Number	1923
Program	Horizon 2020		
Type of Action	Water RIA – Research and Innovation Action		
Start Date	March 1, 2020	Duration	36 months
Project Coordinator	Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain		
Consortium	<p>Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain</p> <p>Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung (UFZ), Germany</p> <p>Università degli Studi di Parma (UNIPR), Italy</p> <p>Boğaziçi Üniversitesi (BU), Turkey</p> <p>Centre de Recherches et des Technologies des Eaux (CERTE), Tunisie</p> <p>Technical University of Crete (TUC), Greece</p> <p>Associação do Instituto Superior Técnico para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento (IST-ID), Portugal</p>		

Document Information

Deliverable Number	D6.2	Deliverable Name	Report on the Results of the DSS for the Case Study Sites	
Work Package number	WP6	Work Package Title	Innovative Decision Support Systems in the MED	
Due Date	Contractual (revised)	February, 2023	Actual	August, 2023
Version Number	2.0			
Deliverable Type	report (R)	Dissemination Level	public (PU)	
Authors	Ioanna Anyfanti, Emmanouil Varouchakis			
Reviewer(s)	George Karatzas Janire Uribe-Asarta Vanessa A. Godoy J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández			

Document History

Version	Date	Stage	Reviewed by
0.1	08/02/2023	First draft	George Karatzas
0.2	13/02/2023	Enrichment	George Karatzas
0.3	23/02/2023	Enrichment	George Karatzas
1.0	02/03/2023	First version	Janire Uribe-Asarta Vanessa A. Godoy J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández
1.1	03/07/2023	Update: second draft	George Karatzas
1.2	21/07/2023	Enrichment	George Karatzas
2.0	02/08/2023	Second version	Janire Uribe-Asarta Vanessa A. Godoy J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández

Table of Contents

Project Information	2
Document Information.....	3
Document History	3
Table of Contents	4
List of Figures	6
List of Tables.....	10
Executive Summary	11
1. Introduction	12
2. Results for the Environmental Criteria.....	13
2.1. Baseline Scenario.....	20
2.2. Climate Change Model 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17'.....	26
2.2.1. RCP 4.5	26
2.2.2. RCP 8.5	32
2.3. Climate Change Model 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M'	38
2.3.1. RCP 4.5	38
2.3.2. RCP 8.5	44
2.4. Climate Change Model 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5'	50
2.4.1. RCP 4.5	50
2.4.2. RCP 8.5	56
2.5. Climate Change Model 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR'.....	62
2.5.1. RCP 4.5	62
2.5.2. RCP 8.5	68
2.6. Climate Change Model 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5'.....	74
2.6.1. RCP 4.5	74
2.6.2. RCP 8.5	80
2.7. Climate Change Model 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4'	86
2.7.1. RCP 4.5	86
2.7.2. RCP 8.5	92
2.8. Discussion of the Results	98
3. The Cost-Benefit Analysis.....	103
3.1. Summary.....	103
3.2. Introduction.....	103

3.3. Case studies: Cost-Benefit Analysis Results	106
4. References	112

List of Figures

Figure 1. Map for the baseline scenario for pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....	20
Figure 2. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the baseline scenario and pumping rates equal to demand	21
Figure 3. Map for the baseline scenario for the current pumping rates at the end of the dry period	22
Figure 4. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the baseline scenario and current pumping rates	23
Figure 5. Map for the baseline scenario for the optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period	24
Figure 6. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the baseline scenario and optimum pumping rates.....	25
Figure 7. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....	26
Figure 8. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP4.5	27
Figure 9. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period	28
Figure 10. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model and current pumping rates - RCP4.5.....	29
Figure 11. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period	30
Figure 12. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model and optimum pumping rates - RCP4.5.....	31
Figure 13. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....	32
Figure 14. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP8.5	33
Figure 15. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period	34
Figure 16. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model and current pumping rates – RCP8.5.....	35
Figure 17. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period	36
Figure 18. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP8.5.....	37
Figure 19. Map for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....	38
Figure 20. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP4.5.....	39

Figure 21. Map for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period40

Figure 22. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' model and current pumping rates - RCP4.541

Figure 23. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period42

Figure 24. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' model and optimum pumping rates - RCP4.543

Figure 25. Map for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....44

Figure 26. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP8.545

Figure 27. Map for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period46

Figure 28. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' model and current pumping rates – RCP8.547

Figure 29. Map for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period48

Figure 30. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP8.5.....49

Figure 31. Map for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....50

Figure 32. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP4.551

Figure 33. Map for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period52

Figure 34. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' model and current pumping rates - RCP4.553

Figure 35. Map for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period54

Figure 36. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP4.5.....55

Figure 37. Map for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....56

Figure 38. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP8.557

Figure 39. Map for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period58

Figure 40. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' model and current pumping rates – RCP8.559

Figure 41. Map for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period60

Figure 42. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP8.5.....61

Figure 43. Map for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....62

Figure 44. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP4.5.....63

Figure 45. Map for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period64

Figure 46. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' model and current pumping rates - RCP4.565

Figure 47. Map for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period66

Figure 48. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' model and optimum pumping rates - RCP4.567

Figure 49. Map for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....68

Figure 50. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP8.5.....69

Figure 51. Map for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period70

Figure 52. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' model and current pumping rates – RCP8.571

Figure 53. Map for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period72

Figure 54. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP8.573

Figure 55. Map for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....74

Figure 56. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP4.5.....75

Figure 57. Map for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period76

Figure 58. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' model and current pumping rates – RCP4.577

Figure 59. Map for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period78

Figure 60. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP4.579

Figure 61. Map for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....80

Figure 62. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP8.5.....81

Figure 63. Map for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period82

Figure 64. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' model and current pumping rates – RCP8.583

Figure 65. Map for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period84

Figure 66. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP8.585

Figure 67. Map for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....86

Figure 68. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' model and current pumping rates - RCP4.5.....87

Figure 69. Map for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period88

Figure 70. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' model and current pumping rates - RCP4.5.....89

Figure 71. Map for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period90

Figure 72. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP4.591

Figure 73. Map for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period.....92

Figure 74. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP8.5.....93

Figure 75. Map for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period94

Figure 76. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' model and current pumping rates – RCP8.595

Figure 77. Map for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period96

Figure 78. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP8.597

Figure 79. Cost benefit analysis flowchart.....108

Figure 80. Country WEI index according to UN SDG 6.4.2 (UN 20022)110

List of Tables

Table 1: List of examined Regional Climate Models	13
Table 2: Results for the distance of the saltwater intrusion front from the shore for RCP4.5.	14
Table 3: Results for the distance of the saltwater intrusion front from the shore for RCP8.5.	14
Table 4: Water demand and current pumping rates per season	14
Table 5: Optimum Pumping Rates (m ³ /day) for the dry period and the examined Regional Climate Models for RCP4.5.....	16
Table 6: Optimum Pumping Rates (m ³ /day) for the dry period and the examined Regional Climate Models for RCP8.5.....	17
Table 7: Optimum Pumping Rates (m ³ /day) for the wet period and the examined Regional Climate Models for RCP4.5.....	18
Table 8: Optimum Pumping Rates (m ³ /day) for the wet period and the examined Regional Climate Models for RCP8.5.....	19
Table 9. Minimum hydraulic head values (m) when considering pumping rates equal to water demand	99
Table 10. Maximum hydraulic head values (m) when considering pumping rates equal to water demand	100
Table 11. Minimum hydraulic head values (m) when considering the current pumping rates	100
Table 12. Maximum hydraulic head values (m) when considering the current pumping rates	101
Table 13. Minimum hydraulic head values (m) when considering optimum pumping rates .	101
Table 14. Maximum hydraulic head values (m) when considering Optimum Pumping Rates	102
Table 15. Proposed water resources distribution in the study areas using in situ data	108
Table 16. Proposed water resources distribution in the study areas using RCP 4.5 and 8.5 for the year 2031	109
Table 17. Proposed water resources distribution in the study areas using RCP 4.5 and 8.5 for the year 2041	109
Table 18. WEI status of each study site	111
Table 19. Necessary groundwater pumping reduction to retain the improved WEI category	111

Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

The current deliverable, namely D6.2, is part of Task 6.2: “Results of the DSS for the Case Study Sites Under Future Scenarios” (Lead TUC, participants: UPV, UFZ, UNIPR, CERTE and BU). The aim of D6.2 is to present the results of the simulation-optimization (S-O) procedure for the Tympaki study area for the baseline scenario of a 30-year period (1975-2005) as well as for a climate change scenario, considering RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 for a period from 1975 until 2040. Additionally, the results of the cost-benefit analysis for the case study sites of Requena-Utiel (Spain), Tympaki (Greece) and Konya (Turkey) are presented.

1. Introduction

In the present work, the results of the integrated socio-economic and environmental approach that was used for the definition of the optimum solution for water management in Tympaki study area are presented. This approach is consisted by two main components:

- the numerical simulation – optimization that is used for the definition of the optimum pumping rates of the wells in the study area,
- the cost – benefit analysis that is used to determine the water resources distribution.

The cost-benefit analysis (CBA) takes into consideration the following variables that function as social and economic criteria: population growth, water demand, crop production and costs. By applying the CBA, the percentage for each available water resource is defined, forming the water budget for the study area. The percentage of groundwater use is applied on the total demand to calculate the groundwater demand. Then, the optimization problem is formed as the maximization of the pumping rates subjected to the following two restrictions:

- the coverage of the total groundwater demand, which stands for the socio-economic criterion,
- the amelioration of the groundwater level by up to 1m above the current situation in order to mitigate saltwater intrusion, which stands for the environmental criterion.

The optimization procedure is linked to the simulation model of the aquifer. Multiple simulations allow us to assess whether a pumping scheme is the optimal one.

The whole process of CBA and simulation optimization contributes to water management decision making by providing the optimal solution based on social needs, economic costs, and environmental constraints as a result. Through these processes, the distribution of water resources is formed, paying special attention to the distribution of groundwater resources

The procedure described above has been applied to both in situ data and climate change models. Section 2 presents the results of the simulation and optimization procedure for the Tympaki site. Section 3 presents the results of the cost-benefit analysis for the study sites of Tympaki (Greece), Requena-Utiel (Spain), and Konya (Turkey).

2. Results for the Environmental Criteria

The piecewise linear approach within the simulation-optimization framework was used to evaluate the environmental criteria, as described in documents D6.1v2 (Varouchakis et al., 2022) and M6.2 (Anyfanti & Diakoparaskevas, 2022). The following sections present the analysis results for the baseline scenario and the climate change models studied. The baseline scenario refers to in situ precipitation data for a 30-year period from 1975 to 2005. The climate change data for each model are from Task 3.3: "Downscaling of Future Climate Projections at the Case Study Scale and their Transfer to the Partners" of WP3 (D'Oria et al., 2022) and refer to the period from 1975 to 2098. The climate change models studied are listed in Table 1 below.

Table 1: List of examined Regional Climate Models

'CNRM_CERFACS_CNRM_CM5_CCLM4_8_17'
'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M'
'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5'
'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR'
'KNMI_CNRM-CM5'
'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4'

All scenarios were run for three different situations:

- (a) For pumping rates corresponding to the water demand for irrigation.
- (b) For the current pumping rates, which represent the allowable values based on water withdrawal rights.
- (c) For the optimal pumping rates derived from the optimization approach.

Tables 2 and 3 show the distance of the saltwater intrusion zone for the regional climate models studied and the respective RCP scenarios. The plotted distance refers to the dry period simulation time step used to calculate the response matrices during the optimization process.

Table 2: Results for the distance of the saltwater intrusion front from the shore for RCP4.5

Distance of saltwater intrusion front from the shore (km) in the middle of the study area coastline for the examined Regional Climate Models - RCP4.5						
Pumping rates	'CNRM_CER FACS_CNR M_CM5_CC LM4_8_17'	'DMI_HIRHA M5_NorES M1-M'	'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIR HAM5'	'IPSL- INERIS_WRF 381P_IPSL- CM5A-MR'	'KNMI_CNR M-CM5'	'MPI_M_M PI_ESM_LR _RCA4'
Equal to demand	2.8	2.7	2.6 (*) 4.5	2.7 (*) 3.6	2.6	2.7
Permitted/Current	1.4	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Optimum	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.3

Table 3: Results for the distance of the saltwater intrusion front from the shore for RCP8.5

Distance of saltwater intrusion front from the shore (km) in the middle of the study area coastline for the examined Regional Climate Models – RCP8.5						
Pumping rates	'CNRM_CER FACS_CNR M_CM5_CC LM4_8_17'	'DMI_HIRHA M5_NorES M1-M'	'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIR HAM5'	'IPSL- INERIS_WRF 381P_IPSL- CM5A-MR'	'KNMI_CNR M-CM5'	'MPI_M_M PI_ESM_LR _RCA4'
Equal to demand	2.6	2.7	2.8	2.8	2.7	2.8
Permitted/Current	1.5	1.5	1.6	1.4	1.4	1.5
Optimum	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.2

The values of the pumping rates that were used for the simulation runs are presented in Table 4, for the groundwater demand and the current pumping rates. The optimization results for the pumping rate of each abstraction well are presented in the following Tables 5 to 8.

Table 4: Water demand and current pumping rates per season

Pumping Well	Demand for the dry season (m ³ /day)	Current pumping-permitted for the dry season (m ³ /day)	Demand for the wet season (m ³ /day)	Current pumping-permitted for the wet season (m ³ /day)
1	1,000	393	110	214
2	12,782	8,699	3,476	8,699
3	27,356	10,258	4,130	8,688
4	310	182	88	63

5	10,448	3,475	2,740	3,420
6	2,274	921	751	921
7	682	175	80	136
8	1,632	474	542	381
9	1,962	1,498	725	816
10	4,378	1,335	831	1,295
11	10,119	3,543	2,371	1,559
12	2,762	1,099	803	951
13	2,904	782	204	211
14	8,642	2,956	1,403	2,410
15	1,562	427	194	349
16	1,386	617	405	418
17	752	363	215	224
18	1,453	561	136	140
19	3,360	1,561	270	268
20	302	163	99	93
Total pumping rates	96,065	39,480	19,573	31,255

Simulation results are presented in the following sections for each regional climate model. The time series of hydraulic head results at the observation points are presented in graphs for the entire simulation period (1975 - 2098). The pumping rates, hydraulic head values at the observation points, and hydraulic head isolines are also shown in the respective maps. The maps show the dry period simulation time step with the minimum observed hydraulic pressure values at the observation points during the 2020-2041 period for which the optimization is performed. The saltwater intrusion front is indicated by the red isoline.

Table 5: Optimum Pumping Rates (m³/day) for the dry period and the examined Regional Climate Models for RCP4.5

Optimum Pumping Rates (m ³ /day) for the dry period and the examined Regional Climate Models – RCP4.5						
Pumping Well	'CNRM_CERFACS_CN RM_CM5_CCLM4_8_17'	'DMI_HIRHAM5_Nor ESM1-M'	'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HI RHAM5'	'IPSL- INERIS_WRF381P_IPS L-CM5A-MR'	'KNMI_CNRM-CM5'	'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_L R_RCA4'
1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	7,550	10,402	0	0	9,641	11,883
4	310	310	0	142	310	0
5	0	0	10,448	10,448	0	0
6	2,274	2,274	2,274	2,056	2,274	2,274
7	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	1,631	1,623	0	0	1,631	753
9	0	0	0	1,962	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	2,762	2,762	2,762	2,762	2,762	2,762
13	2,904	2,904	2,904	2,904	2,904	2,904
14	2,091	0	3,441	0	0	0
15	1,562	1,562	1,562	1,562	1,562	1,562
16	1,386	1,386	0	1,386	1,386	1,386
17	752	0	0	0	752	0
18	1,453	1,453	1,453	1,453	1,453	1,453
19	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	302	302	133	302	302	0
Total pumping rates	24,977	24,977	24,977	24,977	24,977	24,977

Table 6: Optimum Pumping Rates (m³/day) for the dry period and the examined Regional Climate Models for RCP8.5

Optimum Pumping Rates (m ³ /day) for the dry period and the examined Regional Climate Models – RCP8.5						
Pumping Well	'CNRM_CERFACS_CN RM_CM5_CCLM4_8_17'	'DMI_HIRHAM5_Nor ESM1-M'	'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HI RHAM5'	'IPSL- INERIS_WRF381P_IPS L-CM5A-MR'	'KNMI_CNRM-CM5'	'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_L R_RCA4'
1	0	0	1,000	0	0	0
2	0	0	11,060	0	0	828
3	4,486	10,941	0	6,440	3,761	7,765
4	0	0	0	310	310	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	2,274	0	2,274	2,274	2,274	2,274
7	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	1,631	0	1,631	1,631	1,631
9	0	0	1,962	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	2,762	2,762	2,762	2,762	0	2,762
13	2,904	2,904	2,904	2,904	2,904	2,904
14	8,642	364	0	4,255	8,642	0
15	1,562	1,562	1,562	1,562	1,562	1,562
16	0	0	0	1,386	1,386	437
17	0	0	0	0	752	0
18	1,453	1,453	1,453	1,453	1,453	1,453
19	894	3,360	0	0	0	3,360
20	0	0	0	0	302	0
Total pumping rates	24,977	24,977	24,977	24,977	24,977	24,977

Table 7: Optimum Pumping Rates (m³/day) for the wet period and the examined Regional Climate Models for RCP4.5

Optimum Pumping Rates (m ³ /day) for the wet period and the examined Regional Climate Models – RCP4.5							
Pumping Well	'CNRM_CERFACS_CN RM_CM5_CCLM4_8_17'	'DMI_HIRHAM5_Nor ESM1-M'	'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HI RHAM5'	'IPSL- INERIS_WRF381P_IPS L-CM5A-MR'	'KNMI_CNRM-CM5'	'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_L R_RCA4'	
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	1,361	1,361	1,361	1,361	1,361	1,361	1,361
12	803	803	803	803	803	803	803
13	204	204	204	204	204	204	204
14	1,403	1,403	1,403	1,403	1,403	1,403	1,403
15	194	194	194	194	194	194	194
16	405	405	405	405	405	405	405
17	215	215	215	215	215	215	215
18	136	136	136	136	136	136	136
19	270	270	270	270	270	270	270
20	99	99	99	99	99	99	99
Total pumping rates	5,089	5,089	5,089	5,089	5,089	5,089	5,089

Table 8: Optimum Pumping Rates (m³/day) for the wet period and the examined Regional Climate Models for RCP8.5

Optimum Pumping Rates (m ³ /day) for the wet period and the examined Regional Climate Models – RCP8.5							
Pumping Well	'CNRM_CERFACS_CN RM_CM5_CCLM4_8_17'	'DMI_HIRHAM5_Nor ESM1-M'	'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HI RHAM5'	'IPSL- INERIS_WRF381P_IPS L-CM5A-MR'	'KNMI_CNRM-CM5'	'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_L R_RCA4'	
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	1,361	1,361	1,361	1,361	1,361	1,361	1,361
12	803	803	803	803	803	803	803
13	204	204	204	204	204	204	204
14	1,403	1,403	1,403	1,403	1,403	1,403	1,403
15	194	194	194	194	194	194	194
16	405	405	405	405	405	405	405
17	215	215	215	215	215	215	215
18	136	136	136	136	136	136	136
19	270	270	270	270	270	270	270
20	99	99	99	99	99	99	99
Total pumping rates	5,089	5,089	5,089	5,089	5,089	5,089	5,089

2.1. Baseline Scenario

Figure 1. Map for the baseline scenario for pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 2. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the baseline scenario and pumping rates equal to demand

Figure 3. Map for the baseline scenario for the current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 4. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the baseline scenario and current pumping rates

Figure 5. Map for the baseline scenario for the optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 6. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the baseline scenario and optimum pumping rates

2.2. Climate Change Model 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17'

2.2.1. RCP 4.5

Figure 7. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 8. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP4.5

Figure 9. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 10. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model and current pumping rates - RCP4.5

Figure 11. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 12. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model and optimum pumping rates - RCP4.5

2.2.2. RCP 8.5

Figure 13. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 14. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP8.5

Figure 15. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 16. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model and current pumping rates – RCP8.5

Figure 17. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 18. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP8.5

2.3. Climate Change Model 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M'

2.3.1. RCP 4.5

Figure 19. Map for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 20. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP4.5

Figure 21. Map for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 22. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' model and current pumping rates - RCP4.5

Figure 23. Map for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 24. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' model and optimum pumping rates - RCP4.5

2.3.2. RCP 8.5

Figure 25. Map for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 26. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP8.5

Figure 27. Map for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 28. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' model and current pumping rates – RCP8.5

Figure 29. Map for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 30. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP8.5

2.4. Climate Change Model 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5'

2.4.1. RCP 4.5

Figure 31. Map for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 32. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP4.5

Figure 33. Map for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 34. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' model and current pumping rates - RCP4.5

Figure 35. Map for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 36. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP4.5

2.4.2. RCP 8.5

Figure 37. Map for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 38. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP8.5

Figure 39. Map for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 40. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' model and current pumping rates – RCP8.5

Figure 41. Map for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 42. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP8.5

2.5. Climate Change Model 'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR'

2.5.1. RCP 4.5

Figure 43. Map for the 'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 44. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP4.5

Figure 45. Map for the 'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 46. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' model and current pumping rates - RCP4.5

Figure 47. Map for the 'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 48. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' model and optimum pumping rates - RCP4.5

2.5.2. RCP 8.5

Figure 49. Map for the 'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 50. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP8.5

Figure 51. Map for the 'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 52. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' model and current pumping rates – RCP8.5

Figure 53. Map for the 'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 54. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP8.5

2.6. Climate Change Model 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5'

2.6.1. RCP 4.5

Figure 55. Map for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 56. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP4.5

Figure 57. Map for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 58. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' model and current pumping rates – RCP4.5

Figure 59. Map for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 60. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP4.5

2.6.2. RCP 8.5

Figure 61. Map for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 62. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP8.5

Figure 63. Map for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 64. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' model and current pumping rates – RCP8.5

Figure 65. Map for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 66. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP8.5

2.7. Climate Change Model 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4'

2.7.1. RCP 4.5

Figure 67. Map for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 68. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' model and current pumping rates - RCP4.5

Figure 69. Map for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 70. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' model and current pumping rates - RCP4.5

Figure 71. Map for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' climate change model for RCP 4.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 72. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP4.5

2.7.2. RCP 8.5

Figure 73. Map for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and pumping rates equal to demand at the end of the dry period

Figure 74. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' model and pumping rates equal to demand – RCP8.5

Figure 75. Map for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and current pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 76. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' model and current pumping rates – RCP8.5

Figure 77. Map for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' climate change model for RCP 8.5 and optimum pumping rates at the end of the dry period

Figure 78. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells for the 'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4' model and optimum pumping rates – RCP8.5

2.8. Discussion of the Results

Results for the 'CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5-CCLM4-8-17' model are shown in Figures 7 through 12 for the RCP4.5 scenario and Figures 13 through 18 for the RCP8.5 scenario. Considering pumping rates equal to water demand, the saltwater intrusion front is 2.8 km from the shoreline for the RCP4.5 scenario and 2.6 km for the RCP8.5 scenario, as shown in the maps in Figures 7 and 13. The minimum observed value for RCP4.5 is 1.22 m a.s.l. for the 1975-2041 period, while it is 0.73 m a.s.l. for 1975-2098 and the maximum observed value for RCP4.5 is 19.88 m asl for both periods (1975-2041 and 1975-2098), as shown in Figure 8, the plot of hydraulic head values at the observation points.

For the RCP8.5 scenario, the minimum observed value of hydraulic head is 1.50 m a.s.l. for the period from 1975 to 2041, while it is 1.04 m a.s.l. for the period from 1975 to 2098. The maximum observed value is 18.01 m a.s.l. for both periods. The corresponding diagram for the values of hydraulic head in the observation points for the RCP8.5 scenario is shown in Figure 14.

When considering the current or the optimal pumping rates, the saltwater intrusion is attenuated. The saltwater intrusion front is 1.4 km from the shoreline for RCP4.5 (Figure 9) and 1.5 km from the shoreline for RCP8.5 (Figure 15) when the current pumping rates are applied. Accordingly, when the optimal pumping rates are applied, the saltwater intrusion front is 1.2 km from the shoreline for both RCP4.5 (Figure 11) and RCP8.5 (Figure 17). This fact may indicate that the Water Directorate considered measures to limit overuse of the aquifer. However, as the optimization results show, there is still room for improvement. The hydraulic head time series are shown in Figure 10 for the current pumping rates and Figure 12 for the optimal solution for RCP4.5 and Figures 16 and 18 for RCP8.5. For the current pumping rates and the RCP4.5 scenario, the lowest observed value is 4.82 m a.s.l. for the 1975-2041 period and 4.14 m a.s.l. for the 1975-2098 period, and the highest observed value is 21.65 m a.s.l. for both periods (1975-2041 and 1975-2098). For the RCP8.5 scenario, the minimum observed value of hydraulic heads is 5.01 m a.s.l. for the 1975-2041 period, while it is 4.28 m a.s.l. for the 1975-2098 period. When considering the optimum pumping rates, the minimum observed value for RCP4.5 is 5.80 m a.s.l. for the period 1975-2041 and 5.17 m a.s.l. for the period 1975-2098, while the maximum observed value for RCP4.5 is 22.67 m a.s.l. for both periods (1975-

2041 and 1975-2098). For the RCP8.5 scenario, the minimum observed value of hydraulic head is 5.87 m a.s.l. for the period 1975-2041, while it is 5.22 m a.s.l. for the period 1975-2098.

Considering this, the optimization goal of raising the water level by 1 m was achieved within the considered period (2020 - 2041). Between the two periods, before and after 2041, there are differences in the observed minimum values; even using the optimal pumping rates, a drop in the water level is observed after 2041. This is reinforced by the fact that the maximum value of hydraulic head is observed in the first period studied. All this indicates that an update of the optimal solution must be performed if a longer design period is considered. This is quite reasonable, since the percentage of groundwater use from the cost-benefit analysis that is considered refers to the period until 2041. The same conclusions can be drawn from the other regional climate models studied (Figures 19 to 78), except for the 'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5' and 'KNMI_CNRM-CM5' models, where the maximum value of hydraulic head for the RCP8.5 scenarios is observed after 2041. The minimum and maximum values of hydraulic head for each pumping scheme are shown in Tables 9 through 14 below for each RCP scenario, regional climate model, and time period studied.

Table 9. Minimum hydraulic head values (m) when considering pumping rates equal to water demand

		'CNRM_CERFACS_CNRM_CM5_CCLM4_8_17'	'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M'	'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5'	'IPSL-INNERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR'	'KNMI_CNRM-CM5'	'MPI_CM2_3_2_HR2329_LR_RCA4'
RCP4.5	min value 1975 – 2041	1.22	1.38	1.39	1.29	1.17	1.24
	min value 1975 – 2098	0.73	0.60	0.98	0.93	0.94	0.71
RCP8.5	min value 1975 – 2041	1.50	1.52	1.57	1.52	1.38	1.22
	min value 1975 – 2098	1.04	0.66	0.93	0.49	1.16	0.44

Table 10. Maximum hydraulic head values (m) when considering pumping rates equal to water demand

		'CNRM_C ERFACS_C NRM_CM 5_CCLM4 _8_17'	'DMI_HIR HAM5_N orESM1- M'	'ICHEC_EC _EARTH_ HIRHAM5'	'IPSL- INERIS_W RF381P_I PSL- CM5A- MR'	'KNMI_CN RM-CM5'	'MPI_M_ MPI_ESM _LR_RCA4 '
RCP4.5	max value 1975 – 2041	19.88	16.85	17.76	17.65	20.41	18.96
	max value 1975 – 2098	19.88	16.85	17.76	17.65	20.41	18.96
RCP8.5	max value 1975 – 2041	18.01	18.99	17.16	18.14	18.82	18.96
	max value 1975 – 2098	18.01	18.99	17.59	18.14	19.28	18.96

Table 11. Minimum hydraulic head values (m) when considering the current pumping rates

		'CNRM_C ERFACS_C NRM_CM 5_CCLM4 _8_17'	'DMI_HIR HAM5_N orESM1- M'	'ICHEC_E C_EARTH _HIRHAM 5'	'IPSL- INERIS_W RF381P_I PSL- CM5A- MR'	'KNMI_C NRM- CM5'	'MPI_M_ MPI_ESM _LR_RCA4 '
RCP4.5	min value 1975 – 2041	4.82	4.93	4.84	4.69	4.95	4.75
	min value 1975 – 2098	4.14	4.23	4.28	4.14	4.41	4.26
RCP8.5	min value 1975 – 2041	5.01	4.86	4.68	4.95	5.03	4.82
	min value 1975 – 2098	4.28	4.23	4.09	3.93	4.47	3.91

Table 12. Maximum hydraulic head values (m) when considering the current pumping rates

		'CNRM_C ERFACS_C NRM_CM 5_CCLM4 _8_17'	'DMI_HIR HAM5_N orESM1- M'	'ICHEC_E C_EARTH _HIRHAM 5'	'IPSL- INERIS_W RF381P_I PSL- CM5A- MR'	'KNMI_C NRM- CM5'	'MPI_M_ MPI_ESM _LR_RCA4 '
RCP4.5	max value 1975 – 2041	21.65	16.37	17.38	17.49	20.55	19.19
	max value 1975 – 2098	21.65	16.37	17.38	17.49	20.55	19.19
RCP8.5	max value 1975 – 2041	17.10	19.62	17.41	17.17	18.22	19.19
	max value 1975 – 2098	17.10	19.62	20.04	17.17	19.01	19.19

Table 13. Minimum hydraulic head values (m) when considering optimum pumping rates

		'CNRM_C ERFACS_C NRM_CM 5_CCLM4 _8_17'	'DMI_HIR HAM5_N orESM1- M'	'ICHEC_E C_EARTH _HIRHAM 5'	'IPSL- INERIS_W RF381P_I PSL- CM5A- MR'	'KNMI_C NRM- CM5'	'MPI_M_ MPI_ESM _LR_RCA4 '
RCP4.5	min value 1975 – 2041	5.80	5.80	5.79	5.57	5.94	5.56
	min value 1975 – 2098	5.17	5.23	5.23	5.15	5.50	5.23
RCP8.5	min value 1975 – 2041	5.87	5.74	5.62	5.90	5.95	5.75
	min value 1975 – 2098	5.22	5.17	5.00	4.94	5.53	4.95

Table 14. Maximum hydraulic head values (m) when considering Optimum Pumping Rates

		'CNRM_C ERFACS_ CNRM_C M5_CCL M4_8_17 '	'DMI_HIR HAM5_N orESM1- M'	'ICHEC_E C_EARTH _HIRHAM 5'	'IPSL- INERIS_ WRF381P _IPSL- CM5A- MR'	'KNMI_C NRM- CM5'	'MPI_M_ MPI_ESM _LR_RCA 4'
RCP4.5	max value 1975 – 2041	22.67	17.63	18.65	18.39	22.08	20.25
	max value 1975 – 2098	22.67	17.63	18.65	18.39	22.08	20.25
RCP8.5	max value 1975 – 2041	18.23	20.59	18.57	18.24	19.65	20.18
	max value 1975 – 2098	18.23	20.59	21.07	18.24	20.24	20.18

3. The Cost-Benefit Analysis

3.1. Summary

Decision-making is a significant tool in water resources management applications. This work addresses the global management decision dilemma for the sustainability of the groundwater resources of a watershed: should stakeholders use groundwater for irrigation and human consumption, or should they apply alternative schemes to protect groundwater resources? The former constitutes an easy but non-sustainable solution, while the latter protects the groundwater body from over-pumping, avoids the associated over-pumping penalties, and utilizes both surface and groundwater watershed resources. The main question arising in the second case relates to the amount of surface water that can be used, taking into consideration water scarcity and potentially dry hydrological years. Therefore, this proposed decision-making tool will provide a framework of the best management solution for the water needs of the study areas based on the balanced use of surface and groundwater resources, considering ecosystem sustainability and surface and groundwater sustainability. In addition, this work can help decision-makers examine and compare various scenarios using different approaches before making a decision regarding the cost and capacity of a hydrologic/hydraulic project and the varied economic charges that water table limit violations can cause inside an audit interval.

3.2. Introduction

In this report, the proposed cost-benefit analysis methodology, described in detail in deliverable D6.1 (Varouchakis et al. 2022), is applied using institutional datasets collected from the project partners for each case study site (Appendices B, C, D, Varouchakis et al., 2023).

Bayesian decision theory quantifies the yield of various decisions using probabilities and costs that accompany such decisions. Therefore, it was primarily developed to utilize additional information to reduce the risk of uncertain decisions. The basic aim is to choose the decision for which the expected loss is the smallest. The problem is posed in probabilistic terms, and it is assumed that all relevant probabilities are unknown. The probabilistic approach is powerful if the probability distributions are indeed known, but this is often not the case. A common way

to overcome this difficulty is to apply Bayesian decision theory by establishing a prior distribution.

The decision-making process, according to the Bayesian risk, is a methodology that combines the expected loss of a specific decision with the probability, θ , of the loss that will occur. The methodology is based on statistical knowledge that is produced after sampling and using prior knowledge information. The latter is known as “soft information”. The basic characteristics of the Bayesian decision theory are the state parameters θ_i ($i = 0 \dots n$) that correspond to the number of stated decisions, the state of the possible decisions or actions $A(i)$, and the state of the expected loss function that corresponds to each decision, $L(A(i), \theta_i)$. The set θ that considers all the possible state parameters, θ_i , is known as the parametric space. Set A contains all possible actions $A(i)$. A loss function $L(A(i), \theta_i)$ is defined for all $A(i)$, θ_i that belong to $[\theta \times A]$.

The decision-making problem herein has two possible actions as decisions. The first one is to «Continue over-pumping», with probability to pay fines to the authorities related to the number of the over-pumping violations and the second one is to «stop over-pumping and use surface water from potential available sources». Over-pumping violation penalties were used according to information selected by each site for the project partners. Therefore, the two actions A considered for each case study are the following:

- Action $A(0)$: Use only groundwater
- Action $A(1)$: Surface water/groundwater use – Aquifer recharge

Decision-Making Process involves two stages. The first step refers to the state estimation whereas the second one is the Decision Making. For the state estimation, firstly, all the state parameters θ_i are defined. However, in the Bayesian approach a state parameter is an unknown quantity and is considered as a random variable that must be determined. The procedure of each θ_i estimation involves the previous knowledge on the examined issue with the use of the subjective prior distribution $\pi(\theta_i)$ that express the prior information for each state parameter. Next, the Bayesian Risk function is obtained to estimate the optimal decision or the decision with the minimum expected risk. The latter also applies in terms of a cost

benefit analysis procedure and denotes the preferable action. The Bayesian decision making process follows the next steps:

1. Set up the decision-making problem by introducing the possible actions set A and the parametric space θ . The first one is to «Continue of the over-pumping», with probability to pay fines to the authorities related to the number Y of the over-pumping violations and the second one is to «stop over-pumping and use an alternative source that will supply the area with water».
2. Establishment of the expected Loss function for each decision $A(i)$ providing also the state of the Goal function. If at this step the parameters θ_i are considered known, then the decision process is called cost benefit analysis and step 4 is directly applied. If not, a probability distribution expresses θ_i and steps 3 and 4 applies. A binomial distribution is applied to express audits for over-pumping.
3. Development of the subjective prior distributions for each θ_i quantifying the previous information. In the case of the Binomial distribution, the Beta distribution is the conjugate prior distribution.
4. Combine steps 1, 2 and 3 via the Risk function $R=R(A(1))- R(A(0))$ that shows which action is riskier and is described in detail in deliverable D6.1 (Varouchakis et al. 2022). The decision with the minimum expected risk is the optimal. A more detailed description of the aforementioned steps is presented in Appendix A.

The Bayesian decision method is applied in this project to address the dilemma of whether to apply alternative measures for irrigation and drinking water purposes or to apply a groundwater resources management policy in terms of scaled over-pumping (Varouchakis et al., 2016, 2019).

This work provides a tool that considers, besides the Bayesian decision method, a cost-benefit analysis approach to assess the stated dilemma and to help the decision-makers to compare techniques for testing potential strategies for decision dilemmas in hydrological applications.

3.3. Case studies: Cost-Benefit Analysis Results

Three case studies were considered for the application of the proposed cost-benefit analysis methodology: Tympaki, Crete (Greece), Requena-Utiel (Spain), and Konya (Turkey). All the necessary hydrological/hydrogeological data for each case study and management information were collected and provided by partners for each site after the completion of a relative questioner (Appendices B, C, D).

The penalty fine values and loss functions were formed in order the stakeholders and the local managing authorities to develop environmental consciousness and to acquire long-term environmental policy. The penalty values were formed in order their scaled variability based on the potential improper aquifer management to be comparative to the cost of the preferred mitigation measure, which is a long-term solution. The penalty values were based on fines applied by the different water resources management authorities in the study sites and provided by the partners. In the European Union, each member state should assure the sustainability of the water resources and usual practices are the restriction/minimization of pumping in areas with critical water resources availability and during dry periods, or increase of the groundwater volumetric consumption price. Herein, a framework that can be followed in water resources management dilemmas is presented.

An alternative approach to mitigate the area's aquifer is considered, such as surface water use. Thus, the allowed surface water availability volume and relative cost C is considered based on-site information or it is considered unknown and will be calculated in comparison to the groundwater overpumping cost, while the annual operational AC was typically calculated equal to 1% of the mitigation measure cost (Stephenson 2012). The probability ϑ_1 , water demand not to be covered is calculated statistically based on available hydrological data for each case study, while the cost M of transferring water from another source to support the mitigation scheme requirements e.g., local waste water treatment plant effluent for irrigation use, is also considered or unknown when no information available.

On the other hand, the probability ϑ_0 of over-pumping follows the binomial distribution (monitoring of over-pumping i.e., success or failure) with a Beta prior distribution as conjugate according to the literature identified also from the optimal fit of groundwater level variations. This work proposes a scaled variation of the over-pumping cost and of environmental cost due

to the lost value of groundwater. In addition, the groundwater pumping cost GC for the area of the case study is considered where applicable, while the lost value of groundwater as a sustainable source LGV can be calculated considering its potential value as fresh potable water. The potable water on average in the EU costs 0.18 euro/m^3 (Eurostat Water 2021).

Let us consider penalty fines for K_1 , K_2 , and K_3 according to section 2.1.1 of the 6.1 deliverable and Appendix A, to increase linearly as a function of the per capita income of each country for the first, second, and third intervals of violations and that n_1 is equal to 6 and n_2 is equal to 18 successful audits. The total auditing interval is assumed equal to $N = 36$. On the other hand, the surface water cost C , and respective volume is calculated as a function of the groundwater volume through the hydrological demand balance, while the surface and ground water irrigation cost were considered 0.08 and 0.1 euro/m^3 on average in the EU (Eurostat Water 2021). In the case study, it is assumed that the authorities perform monthly audits for over-pumping. The methodological steps to calculate the Bayesian risk and to apply the cost-benefit analysis are based on MATLAB code presented in Varouchakis et al. 2016, 2019.

In Bayesian risk methodology, prior information is applied by fitting the available data to the most suitable probability distribution function. Herein, the probability that over-pumping and a drought year to occur or the necessary surface water is not available is denoted as a “success” and the opposite as a “failure” and the appropriate conjugative prior distribution that matches with Binomial distribution is the beta distribution. Therefore, annual water table level variation and rainfall data are fitted to the beta distribution. The distribution’s shape parameters values α and β are validated using the mean and the variance functions of the beta distribution (Lerche and Paleologos 2001). By applying the risk function for each suggested decision, it is obtained that the most preferable action for every site is to apply the proposed mitigation measure $A(1)$, e.g., $R(A(1)) < R(A(0))$ combining groundwater/surface water resources exploitation percentages. The results for each case study accompanied by the relative uncertainty of estimations are presented in Table 15. The provided water resources distribution is obtained from the water resources balance presented in the following flowchart by means of the reported water demand for each site and the Bayes risk method principles.

Figure 79. Cost benefit analysis flowchart

Considering the available information and applying the proposed cost benefit analysis methodology described in detail in deliverable D6.1 (Varouchakis et al. 2022) it is obtained that for Tympaki case study up to 15 over-pumping violations are allowed before the mitigation measure is more affordable compared to intensive groundwater use only. On the other hand, for Requena-Utiel (Spain) 16 violations are enough to overcome the mitigation measure cost and in Konya (Turkey) the allowed calculated violations are equal to 12.

Table 15. Proposed water resources distribution in the study areas using in situ data

Case studies	Konya, Turkey	Requena-Utiel, Spain	Tympaki, Greece
Groundwater use	38%±8	34%±2	28%±3
Surface water use	36%±5	44%±3	54%±3
Other sources e.g., waste water treatment plant effluent	26%±6	22%±5	18%±8
Aquifer recharge/to retain improved WEI status	75%±9 of groundwater use	69%±5 of groundwater use	71%±6 of groundwater use

The proposed sustainable water resources use and management in each case study processing in situ data from the study sites and under the mean weighted moving average impact of the examined climate change models (Table 1), downscaled for each site, is presented in the following tables (Table 16-17).

Table 16. Proposed water resources distribution in the study areas using RCP 4.5 and 8.5 for the year 2031

Case studies	Konya, Turkey	Requena-Utiel, Spain	Tympaki, Greece
Groundwater use	44%±5	37%±6	35%±6
Surface water use	32%±6	35%±7	48%±5
Other sources e.g., waste water treatment plant effluent	24%±8	28%±8	17%±9
Aquifer recharge/to retain improved WEI status	71%±12 of groundwater use	68%±10 of groundwater use	73%±11 of groundwater use

Table 17. Proposed water resources distribution in the study areas using RCP 4.5 and 8.5 for the year 2041

Case studies	Konya, Turkey	Requena-Utiel, Spain	Tympaki, Greece
Groundwater use	37%±8	34%±6	26%±3
Surface water use	39%±5	42%±3	61%±3
Other sources e.g., /waste water treatment plant effluent	24%±6	24%±5	13%±6
Aquifer recharge/to retain improved WEI status	73%±11 of groundwater use	71%±9 of groundwater use	76%±8 of groundwater use

Considering absolute volume values, the proposed water resources distribution to ensure sustainability of groundwater resources is as follows:

- Konya, Turkey (water resources demand: 568 10⁶ m³): 215.84±45 10⁶ m³ groundwater use, 204.48 ±28 10⁶ m³ surface water use, 147.68 ±34 10⁶ m³ from other sources.
- Requena-Utiel, Spain (water resources demand: 27 10⁶ m³): 9.18±0.55 10⁶ m³ groundwater use, 11.88 ±0.81 10⁶ m³ surface water use, 5.94 ±34 10⁶ m³ from other sources.
- Tympaki, Greece (water resources demand: 22 10⁶ m³): 6.16±0.66 10⁶ m³ groundwater use, 11.88 ±0.66 10⁶ m³ surface water use, 3.96 ±1.76 10⁶ m³ from other sources.

In addition, the cost-benefit analysis is approached in relation to the Water Exploitation Index (WEI - ratio of water resources use/availability) based on the relevant UN SDG 6.4.2 (UN 2022) to assess the impact of the proposed water resources management options and succeed the improvement of WEI for each case study. The WEI is a water scarcity indicator that provides information on the level of pressure exerted by human activities on the natural water resources of a territory. This helps to identify the areas that are prone to water stress problems. The Water Exploitation Index measures water consumption as a percentage of the renewable freshwater resources available at river sub-basin level and by each of the four quarters of the year (UN 2022). Furthermore, the cost-benefit analysis model provides estimates of the required natural aquifer recharge to retain the improved WEI category by means of improved ratio of groundwater resources use/availability. This is succeeded by adding constraints in the water balance through the cost benefit model code to consider the minimum groundwater volume to retain the ratio of groundwater resources use/availability in the specific scale.

According to the UN SDG 6.4.2 (SDG#6 – 06.41 (UN 2022) Water exploitation index) “level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources (2019)” the countries where the InTheMED sites are located belong to the following categories:

Figure 80. Country WEI index according to UN SDG 6.4.2 (UN 2022)

Considering the available data, the freshwater resource in each site is mainly groundwater. Processing the demand (in situ data) over the availability of freshwater resources (GRACE project), then WEI of each site is calculated (Table 18).

Table 18. WEI status of each study site

Case studies	Konya, Turkey	Requena-Utiel, Spain	Tympaki, Greece
WEI	75-100 high	50-75 Medium	50-75 Medium

The cost-benefit analysis model processing the available surface and groundwater data from each site proposes sustainable water resources use and management in each case study by exploiting the use of alternative water resources (surface water) to improve this metrics (reducing groundwater use). Table 19 determines the necessary groundwater use reduction compared to the current conditions (calculated on average from the assessed scenarios) to retain the improved WEI category (Tables 15 – 17).

Table 19. Necessary groundwater pumping reduction to retain the improved WEI category

Case studies	Konya, Turkey	Requena-Utiel, Spain	Tympaki, Greece
Improved WEI	> 60% groundwater pumping reduction: 25-50 low	> 55% groundwater pumping reduction: 0-25 no stress	> 58% groundwater pumping reduction: 0-25 no stress

Considering the significance of groundwater resources management from environmental and social perspectives, the available water resources data at each site, as well as the optimal Bayesian decision and the calculated probability delivered by the cost-benefit approach, a long-term solution to the water resources management and use of the case study areas is proposed. The proposed tool provides decision-makers the ability to assess different scenarios in terms of variable water resources management and use options before deciding.

4. References

- D'Oria, Marco, Secci, Daniele, Tanda, Maria Giovanna, Todaro, Valeria, & Zanini, Andrea. (2022). InTheMED WP3 Data Archive - Climate Projections in the Case Studies - (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7247977>
- Eurostat Water. (2021). European Commission: Brussels.
- Lerche, I., and Paleologos, E. K. (2001). Environmental risk analysis. McGraw-Hill.
- UN (2022). The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2022, United Nations
- Varouchakis EA, Palogos I, Karatzas GP (2016) Application of Bayesian and cost benefit risk analysis in water resources management. J Hydrol 534:390-396 doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2016.01.007>
- Varouchakis EA, Yetilmezsoy K, Karatzas GP (2019) A decision-making framework for sustainable management of groundwater resources under uncertainty: combination of Bayesian risk approach and statistical tools. Water Policy 21:602-622 doi:10.2166/wp.2019.128
- Varouchakis Emmanouil, Lyronis Antonis, Anyfanti Ioanna, & Diakoparaskevas Paraskevas. (2022). InTheMED D6.1 Report on the Development of the Innovative DSS Tool (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6304566>
- Varouchakis, Emmanouil, Lyronis, Antonios, & Anyfanti, Ioanna. (2021). InTheMED M6.1 Initial DSS Algorithm at an Operational Level (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5748050>
- Varouchakis, Emmanouil, A.Godoy, Vanessa, & Daloğlu Çetinkaya, Irem. (2023). InTheMED D6.2 Report on the Results of the DSS for the Case Study Sites – Appendices B, C and D. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8192393>

Appendix A

Methods and Procedures

Groundwater sustainability depends on the availability of surface waters that due to ecosystem viability only a part of them can be used. So initially a hydrological design should be performed considering the historical data of the watershed in order to determine the hydrological balance.

The proposed controlled water resources management affects positively the sustainability of groundwater. Water needs (W) are supposed to be covered by surface water S and groundwater (G).

$$W = S + G$$

The decision-making process involves two stages: state estimation (equations that express the proposed actions) and decision making. For state estimation, firstly, all the state parameters are defined. However, in the Bayesian approach, a state parameter is an unknown quantity and is considered a random variable that must be determined. The procedure of estimating each parameter involves previous knowledge on the examined issue and the use of the subjective prior distribution that expresses the prior information for each state parameter. Next, the Bayesian risk function is obtained to estimate the optimal decision or the decision with the minimum expected risk. The latter also applies in terms of a cost-benefit analysis procedure and denotes the preferable action. The Bayesian decision-making process follows these four steps:

Set up the decision-making problem by introducing the possible actions set and the parametric space. Establish the expected loss function for each decision.

In this proposal two actions are considered

Action A(0): use only groundwater

Action A(1): combined groundwater surface water use-aquifer recharge

The use of groundwater only as a major source can easily lead to overexploitation. Over-pumping violation policy is proposed to be based on a scaled parabolic penalty function with scaling coefficient (K) that varies with the frequency (n) of violations because of the importance of the problem. Y is random variable that includes the probability of over-pumping during an auditing period. Its expression is given below in terms of Loss functions:

$$L(A(0), Y) = \begin{cases} K_1 Y^2 + G + LGV, & 0 \leq Y \leq n_1 \\ K_2 Y^2 + G + LGV, & n_1 < Y \leq n_2, \\ K_3 Y^2 + G + LGV, & Y > n_2 \end{cases}$$

$$K_1 < K_2 < K_3,$$

where G denotes the groundwater cost (pumping and volume) and LGV the lost value of groundwater as a sustainable source as soon as it is removed from the aquifer (Paleologos, 2008).

Whereas for the $A(1)$ the following applies

$$L(A(1), Y_1) = C + AC + MY_1$$

where, C is the cost of the alternative option and AC is the annual operational cost for the examined auditing period. If one considers the case that there is a risk (probability) Y_1 the surface water not to provide sufficient water during drought years or the watershed may not have the appropriate surface water resources, an additional cost M is applied, denoting an additional water supply (e.g., water transport, groundwater) that should be considered. Thus, Y_1 is a random variable that includes the unknown probability the surface water not to cover the necessary volume. Both Y and Y_1 are expressed by probability density functions.

Provide the state of the goal function. If, at this step, the parameters are considered known, then the decision process is called a cost-benefit analysis, and Step 4 is directly applied. If not, then both Steps 3 and 4 apply.

The goal function is the expected value of the loss function. Thus, for actions $A(0), A(1)$, the goal functions are expressed as follows:

$$G(A(0), \theta_0) = E[L(A(0), Y)].$$

$$G(A(1), \theta_1) = E[C + AC + MY_1] = C + AC + ME[Y_1].$$

If ϑ_0 and ϑ_1 the state parameters (probabilities) considered known from hydrological information then the cost benefit approach applies leading straight to action quantification that can support a decision.

Develop the subjective prior distributions for each parameter quantifying the previous information.

If ϑ_0 and ϑ_1 the state parameters (probabilities) considered unknown then Bayesian analysis is applied in the terms of the Bayesian Risk function that considers prior information in terms of probability density functions to determine Y and Y_1 .

$$R(A(0)) = \int_0^1 G(A(0), \theta_0) \pi(\theta_0) d\theta_0.$$

$$R(A(1)) = \int_0^1 G(A(1), \theta_1) \pi(\theta_1) d\theta_1$$

where $\pi(\theta)$ denotes the prior distribution in each case that depends on the fitted probability density function to the data. The probability that over-pumping or a drought year would occur or the necessary surface water would not be available is denoted as a “success” and as a “failure” otherwise. Therefore, the probability a “success” will occur corresponds to θ , while the “failure” probability is $1 - \theta$.

Combine Steps 1, 2, and 3 via the risk function. The decision with the minimum expected risk is the optimal decision.

If $R(A(1)) > R(A(0))$, then $A(0)$ is the preferable decision. The $A(1)$ is the optimal action if the opposite applies.